

Energytran

Inventory of research infrastructure (RI) for energy transition: hydrogen and lithium

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Inventory of research infrastructure for energy transition: hydrogen and lithium

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EULAC for Energy Transition

Research infrastructure cooperation for energy
transition between European and Latin
American and the Caribbean countries

ENERGYTRAN PROJECT**EULAC for Energy Transition**

Research infrastructure cooperation for energy transition between European and Latin American and the Caribbean countries

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Introduction

The Energytran inventory is a mapping of scientific infrastructure across the European Union, Latin America, and the Caribbean (EULAC) focusing on research groups and specialized equipment associated, directly or indirectly, with the lithium and hydrogen value chains for energy transition. It compiles statistics on research teams, their institutional affiliations, and the description of major equipment that can be used to support the agenda of research and innovation in energy transition. This inventory offers an overview of EULAC's capabilities for material synthesis, manufacturing, characterization, process design, and performance testing in the areas of lithium processing and valorization, fabrication of lithium-ion batteries, fuel cells, electrolyzers, and novel materials for the production, storage, and valorization of green hydrogen, among other topics of interest in energy transition.

Lithium and green hydrogen play pivotal roles in the worldwide energy transition. The EULAC scientific community has complementary capabilities and resources to contribute to the resolution of the current technological challenges associated with their supply chains to achieve decarbonization goals.

By identifying and collecting the basic information of actors and resources, this inventory aims to foster cooperation and collaboration, enhance knowledge exchange, identify options for training technical staff, establish national and international networks, generate synergies, and support the development of EULAC scientific ecosystem in energy transition. It also serves as a source of basic statistics for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and academic institutions seeking to align research efforts and identify opportunities for cooperation with other partners at national and international levels.

The inventory was integrated with public information obtained from open scientific databases and sources of institutes/facilities of affiliations of EULAC researchers. It includes:

- Statistics of more than 1800 researchers from 575 affiliations of 39 EULAC countries (see Figure 1 and Table 1) categorized by topic: lithium or hydrogen.
- Summary of specialized scientific equipment categorized by institution/facility.

This inventory contains examples of the equipment available in the institutes/facilities of researchers' affiliation; consequently, it is not an exhaustive compilation of the scientific infrastructure of all affiliations.

The content of this inventory provides a picture of EULAC's strengths and capabilities in energy transition. This inventory is a deliverable of the project Energytran - EULAC for energy transition: Research infrastructures cooperation for energy transition between EU and LAC countries, which is an international scientific cooperation initiative funded by the Horizon Europe program.

Introduction

Figure 1. EULAC researchers reported per country in the Energytran inventory of research infrastructure for energy transition (lithium and green hydrogen).

Table 1. Statistics of EULAC researchers and institutes/facilities reported in the Energytran inventory of research infrastructure for energy transition (lithium and green hydrogen).

Country	Researchers	Affiliations	Country	Researchers	Affiliations
Argentina	80	27	Ireland	16	8
Austria	33	9	Italy	254	51
Belgium	32	9	Latvia	3	2
Bolivia	4	2	Lithuania	3	2
Brazil	194	66	Luxembourg	8	2
Bulgaria	9	4	Malta	6	2
Chile	101	23	Mexico	193	54
Colombia	54	22	Netherlands	54	11
Costa Rica	11	5	Paraguay	1	1
Croatia	10	5	Peru	18	11
Cyprus	6	2	Poland	84	22
Czechia	23	12	Portugal	43	13
Denmark	36	6	Romania	14	8
Ecuador	12	8	Slovakia	10	4
Estonia	4	2	Slovenia	10	3
Finland	18	6	Spain	157	45
France	85	39	Sweden	48	8
Germany	192	63	Uruguay	2	1
Greece	35	12	Venezuela	1	1
Hungary	5	4			

The objective of the Energytran project is to help EULAC decarbonization by addressing energy transition as a common challenge throughout the exchange, generation, and transfer of knowledge between the research infrastructures of the EU and LAC from a multidisciplinary approach (technological, environmental, and social). The Energytran project is a platform for generating knowledge and capabilities that contribute to the agenda of the main EULAC stakeholders in the energy transition.

The Energytran EULAC inventory on energy transition is intended to support strategic planning, promote international partnerships, and contribute to the advancement of

sustainable energy technologies through informed decision-making and resource optimization.

Research groups

Argentina

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Asociación Argentina del Hidrógeno	1	-
Comisión de Investigaciones Científicas	-	2
Comisión Nacional de Energía Atómica Argentina	2	2
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	4	10
Instituto de Astronomía y Física del Espacio	-	1
Instituto de Desarrollo Tecnológico para la Industria Química	-	1
Instituto de Desarrollo y Diseño	-	4
Instituto de Investigaciones en Catálisis y Petroquímica	-	1
Instituto de Investigaciones en Energía no Convencional	-	3
Instituto de Investigación en Tecnología Química	-	1
Instituto de Investigaciones para la Industria Química	-	1
Servicio Geológico Minero Argentino	-	2
Universidad de Buenos Aires	2	7
Universidad Nacional de Catamarca	1	-
Universidad Nacional de Córdoba	-	8
Universidad Nacional de Cuyo	-	4
Universidad Nacional de Jujuy	-	2
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	1	3
Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata	-	1
Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto	-	2
Universidad Nacional de Rosario	-	1
Universidad Nacional de Salta	-	1
Universidad Nacional de San Luis	1	1
Universidad Nacional de San Martín	2	2
Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero	-	1
Universidad Nacional del Sur	1	1
Universidad Tecnológica Nacional	1	2
	16	64

Austria

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
AVL List GmbH	1	-
Fachhochschule Oberösterreich	2	-
HyCentA Research GmbH	1	-

Research infrastructures cooperation for energy transition between European and Latin American and the Caribbean countries

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Montanuniversität Leoben	9	-
Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften	2	-
Rouge H ₂ Engineering AG	1	-
Technische Universität Graz	9	-
Technische Universität Wien	5	-
Universität für Bodenkultur Wien	1	2
	31	2

Belgium

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
European Commission Joint Research Centre	2	-
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	1	-
Université catholique de Louvain	2	2
Université de Mons	2	-
Université libre de Bruxelles	5	-
Universiteit Antwerpen	2	-
Universiteit Gent	9	1
Universiteit Hasselt	2	-
Vrije Universiteit Brussel	4	-
	29	3

Bolivia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universidad Católica Boliviana San Pablo	-	1
Universidad Mayor de San Andrés	-	3
	-	4

Brazil

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Centro Nacional de Pesquisa em Energia e Materiais	2	-
Embraer - Empresa Brasileira de Aeronáutica SA	-	1
Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa Agropecuária - Embrapa	-	1
Universidade Federal de Itajubá	2	2
Instituto de Aeronautica e Espaço	-	1
Instituto de Pesquisas Energeticas e Nucleares	-	1
Instituto de Tecnologia Edson Mororó Moura	-	1
Instituto Federal de Educação Ciência e Tecnologia Farroupilha	-	1
Instituto Federal de Educação, Ciência e Tecnologia do Ceará	-	1
Instituto Federal de Mato Grosso do Sul	-	1
Instituto Federal do Amazonas	-	1
Instituto Federal do Norte de Minas Gerais	-	1
Instituto Militar de Engenharia	-	2
Instituto Nacional de Tecnologia	-	1
Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica	1	1
Laboratório Nacional de Luz Síncrotron	-	1
Micropower Energia	-	1
Modecom	1	-
Pontificia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro	3	3
Research Centre for Greenhouse Gas Innovation	1	-
Serviço Nacional de Aprendizagem Industrial - SENAI	4	2
Universidade de Brasília	1	2
Universidade de Pernambuco	-	2
Universidade de São Paulo	6	15
Universidade do Estado de Santa Catarina	-	1
Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro	1	1
Universidade Estadual de Campinas	4	11
Universidade Estadual de Londrina	-	1
Universidade Estadual de Maringá	-	1
Universidade Estadual do Oeste do Paraná	2	-
Universidade Estadual do Piauí	-	1
Universidade Estadual Paulista "Júlio de Mesquita Filho"	2	5
Universidade Federal da Integração Latino-Americana	-	1
Universidade Federal da Paraíba	-	4
Universidade Federal de Alfenas	-	1
Universidade Federal de Campina Grande	-	2
Universidade Federal de Goiás	-	3
Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso	-	1
Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	1	3
Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto	-	4

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universidade Federal de Pelotas	1	1
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco	-	1
Universidade Federal de Roraima	2	-
Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina	-	2
Universidade Federal de Santa Maria	-	3
Universidade Federal de São Carlos	6	7
Universidade Federal de Sao Joao del-Rei	-	1
Universidade Federal de São Paulo	-	2
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia	-	1
Universidade Federal de Viçosa	-	2
Universidade Federal do ABC	-	1
Universidade Federal do Amazonas	-	2
Universidade Federal do Ceará	1	-
Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo	3	2
Universidade Federal do Maranhão	-	1
Universidade Federal do Parana	1	2
Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro	3	7
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte	2	4
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul	2	8
Universidade Federal dos Vales do Jequitinhonha e Mucuri	-	1
Universidade Federal Fluminense	-	3
Universidade Federal Rural de Pernambuco	-	1
Universidade Presbiteriana Mackenzie	-	1
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná	-	4
Université Fédérale de Sergipe	-	1
Universidade de São Paulo	1	1
	53	141

Bulgaria

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Българска академия на науките	5	-
Русенски университет	2	-
Софийски университет "Св. Климент Охридски"	1	-
Технически университет-София	1	-
	9	-

Chile

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	11	6
Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso	3	3
Universidad Andrés Bello	-	1
Universidad Arturo Prat del Estado de Chile	-	4
Universidad Autónoma de Chile	2	-
Universidad Católica de Temuco	-	1
Universidad Católica del Norte	-	6
Universidad de Antofagasta	-	9
Universidad de Atacama	-	3
Universidad de Chile	2	11
Universidad de Concepción	1	5
Universidad de La Frontera	-	3
Universidad de La Serena	-	1
Universidad de O'Higgins	-	1
Universidad de Santiago de Chile	3	4
Universidad de Talca	1	2
Universidad de Tarapacá	3	-
Universidad del Bío-Bío	2	-
Universidad del Desarrollo	1	-
Universidad Mayor	1	1
Universidad San Sebastián	-	1
Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María	3	2
Universidad Tecnológica Metropolitana	-	4
	33	68

Colombia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Fundación Universitaria Los Libertadores	-	2
Institución Universitaria CESMAG	-	1
Institución Universitaria Digital de Antioquia	-	1
Institución Universitaria Pascual Bravo	1	3
Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano	-	5
Tecnológico de Antioquia	1	-
Universidad Católica Luis Amigó	1	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universidad de Antioquia	-	11
Universidad de Córdoba	-	1
Universidad de Ibagué	1	-
Universidad de la Costa	-	1
Universidad de Los Andes	-	2
Universidad de Medellín	-	1
Universidad de Santander	1	-
Universidad de Sucre	-	1
Universidad del Atlántico	-	1
Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas	-	1
Universidad EAFIT	-	2
Universidad Industrial de Santander	-	2
Universidad Nacional de Colombia	4	5
Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana	3	1
Universidad Tecnológica de Pereira	-	1
	12	42

Costa Rica

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Centro Nacional de Alta Tecnología (CeNAT)	-	1
Consejo Nacional de Rectores (CONARE)	-	1
Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica	2	-
Universidad de Costa Rica	6	-
Universidad Nacional de Costa Rica	-	1
	8	3

Croatia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Institut Ruđer Bošković	1	-
Sveučilište Josipa Jurja Strossmayera u Osijeku	2	-
Sveučilište u Rijeci	4	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Sveučilište u Splitu	1	-
Sveučilište u Zagrebu	2	-
	10	-

Cyprus

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου	5	-
Τεχνολογικό Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου	1	-
	6	-

Czechia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Akademie věd České republiky	2	-
České vysoké učení technické v Praze	3	-
Fyzikální ústav Akademie věd České republiky	1	-
Masarykova univerzita	2	-
Ostravská Univerzita	1	-
Technická Univerzita v Liberci	1	-
Univerzita Jana Evangelisty Purkyně v Ústí nad Labem	1	-
Univerzita Pardubice	-	1
Ústav fyzikální chemie J. Heyrovského	1	1
Vysoká škola chemicko-technologická	2	-
Vysoké učení technické v Brně	2	4
Západočeská univerzita v Plzni	1	-
	17	6

Denmark

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Aalborg Universitet	16	-
Aarhus Universitet	6	-
Danfoss AS	1	-
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	11	-
De Nationale Geologiske Undersøgelser for Danmark og Grønland	1	-
Syddansk Universitet	1	-
	36	-

Ecuador

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Escuela Superior Politécnica del Litoral	3	-
Universidad de Cuenca	-	2
Universidad de las Fuerzas Armadas ESPE	-	2
Universidad Nacional de Loja	-	1
Universidad Politécnica Salesiana	-	1
Universidad Técnica de Ambato	-	1
Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja	-	1
Universidad Tecnológica ECOTEC	1	-
	4	8

Estonia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Eesti Maaülikool	1	-
Tartu Ülikool	3	-
	4	-

Finland

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Aalto Yliopisto	5	-
Helsingin Yliopisto	-	2
Lappeenrannan Teknillinen Yliopisto	4	4
Tampere Yliopisto	1	-
Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT	1	-
Turun Yliopisto	1	-
	12	6

France

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Arts et Métiers	5	-
Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	1	-
CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	7	-
École Nationale Supérieure de Techniques Avancées Bretagne	2	-
École nationale supérieure d'ingénieurs de Caen - ENSICAEN	1	-
École Supérieure des Technologies Industrielles Avancées	1	-
ENGIE Lab CRIGEN	1	-
Fuel Cell LAB	1	-
Géosciences Environnement Toulouse	-	1
Geostock	2	-
IFP Energies nouvelles	3	-
IMT Atlantique	1	-
INERIS Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques	1	-
Institut de la Corrosion	1	-
Institut Lavoisier de Versailles	1	-
Institut NÉEL	1	-
L'Organisation de coopération et de développement économiques	1	-
NEOMA Business School	1	-
Normandie Université	1	-
ONERA Office National d'Etudes et Recherches Aérospatiales	2	-
SOLEIL Synchrotron	1	-
Université Bourgogne Franche-Comté	1	-

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Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Université de Bretagne Occidentale	1	-
Université de Caen Normandie	1	-
Université de La Réunion	4	-
Université de Lille	1	-
Université de Lorraine	10	-
Université de Montpellier	2	-
Nantes Université	4	-
Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour	6	-
Université de Poitiers	1	-
Université de Rennes	1	-
Université de Technologie de Belfort-Montbéliard	1	-
Université de Toulouse	2	-
Université d'Orléans	3	-
Université Grenoble Alpes	8	-
Université Paris-Saclay	1	-
Université PSL (Paris Sciences & Lettres)	1	-
Université Savoie Mont Blanc	1	-
	84	1

Germany

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Bergische Universität Wuppertal	1	-
Hochschule Bonn-Rhein-Sieg	1	-
Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel	4	-
Max-Planck-Institut für Chemische Physik fester Stoffe	1	-
Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY	3	-
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Geoforschung (GFZ)	1	-
Deutsches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung	1	-
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR)	11	-
Europa-Universität Flensburg	2	-
Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	4	-
Fraunhofer-Institut für Integrierte Systeme und Bauelementetechnologie IISB	1	-
Fraunhofer-Institut für Windenergiesysteme	1	-
Fraunhofer-Einrichtung für Energieinfrastrukturen und Geotechnologien IEG	1	-
Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft	2	-
Fraunhofer-Institut für Gießerei-, Composite- und Verarbeitungstechnik IGCV	1	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Freie Universität Berlin	1	-
Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	4	-
Gesellschaft für Anlagen- und Reaktorsicherheit (GRS) gGmbH	1	-
Gesellschaft für Chemische Technik und Biotechnologie e.V.	1	-
Helmholtz-Institute Ulm	2	-
Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	16	1
Hochschule Heilbronn	2	-
Hochschule Rhein-Waal	1	-
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	-	2
IAV GmbH Ingenieurgesellschaft Auto und Verkehr	1	-
Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg	4	-
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie	17	1
Leibniz Institut für Katalyse	3	-
Leibniz-Institut für Festkörper- und Werkstoffforschung Dresden	-	1
Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF) e. V.	-	1
Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung	3	-
Max-Planck-Institut für Intelligente Systeme	1	-
Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Regensburg	1	-
Universität Paderborn	1	-
Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen	11	-
RheinMain Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften	2	-
Ruhr-Universität Bochum	2	-
Technische Hochschule Augsburg	1	-
Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt	-	4
Technische Hochschule Köln	1	-
Technische Hochschule Würzburg-Schweinfurt	1	-
Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg	3	-
Technische Universität Berlin	8	1
Technische Universität Braunschweig	1	-
Technische Universität Clausthal	9	-
Technische Universität Darmstadt	1	-
Technische Universität Dresden	1	-
Technische Universität Hamburg	3	-
Technische Universität München	8	-
Universität Bayreuth	6	-
Universität Bremen	2	1
Helmut-Schmidt-Universität - Universität der Bundeswehr Hamburg	1	-
Universität der Bundeswehr München	1	-
Universität Freiburg	1	-
Universität Hamburg	1	-
Universität Hohenheim	1	-
Universität Kassel	1	-
Universität Leipzig	2	-

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Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universität Regensburg	2	-
Universität Rostock	2	-
Universität Stuttgart	10	-
Universität zu Köln	2	-
Universität Münster	1	1
	179	13

Greece

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas	1	-
National Centre for Scientific Research "DEMOKRITOS"	7	-
Ανώτατη Σχολή Παιδαγωγικής και Τεχνολογικής Εκπαίδευσης	1	-
Εθνικό Κέντρο Έρευνας και Τεχνολογικής Ανάπτυξης (ΕΚΕΤΑ)	3	-
ΕΘΝΙΚΟ ΜΕΤΣΟΒΙΟ ΠΟΛΥΤΕΧΝΕΙΟ (ΝΤΥΑ)	9	-
Πανεπιστήμιο Αιγαίου	1	-
Πανεπιστήμιο Δυτικής Αττικής	1	-
Πανεπιστήμιο Δυτικής Μακεδονίας	1	-
Πανεπιστήμιο Θεσσαλίας	4	-
Πανεπιστήμιο Κρήτης	3	-
Πανεπιστήμιο Πατρών	1	-
Πολυτεχνείο Κρήτης	3	-
	35	0

Hungary

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	1	-
Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem	2	-
Magyar Tudományos Akadémia MTA	1	-
Miskolci Egyetem	1	-
	5	-

Ireland

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Aalborg Universitet	1	-
Dublin City University	5	-
Economic and Social Research Institute	1	-
Trinity College Dublin	1	-
University College Cork	2	-
University College Dublin	3	-
University of Galway	1	-
University of Limerick	2	-
	16	-

Italy

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna	8	2
ASM TERNI S.p.A.	1	-
Centro Italiano Ricerche Aerospaziali	2	-
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	12	1
ENI S.p.A.	4	-
Ente Per Le Nuove Tecnologie, l'Energia e l'Ambiente	15	-
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia	3	1
Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale	4	-
Kiwa Cermet	1	-
KT - Kinetics Technology S.p.A	1	-
Parthenope University of Naples	4	-
Politecnico di Bari	5	-
Politecnico di Milano	12	3
Politecnico di Torino	18	5
Sapienza Università di Roma	8	1
Sotacarbo SpA	2	-
Università Campus Bio-Medico di Roma	1	-
Università degli Studi del Sannio	1	-
Università degli Studi della Tuscia	-	1
Università degli Studi dell'Aquila	3	-
Università degli Studi di Bergamo	3	1

Research infrastructures cooperation for energy transition between European and Latin American and the Caribbean countries

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Università degli Studi di Brescia	1	3
Università degli Studi di Cagliari	4	-
Università degli Studi di Firenze	5	-
Università degli Studi di Foggia	1	-
Università degli Studi di Genova	5	2
Università degli Studi di Messina	1	-
Università degli Studi di Milano	1	-
Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia	8	-
Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	14	-
Università degli Studi di Padova	7	-
Università degli Studi di Palermo	7	-
Università di Pavia	3	2
Università degli Studi di Perugia	7	-
Università degli Studi di Roma Tor Vergata	4	-
Università degli Studi di Salerno	4	-
Università degli Studi di Sassari	2	-
Università di Torino	6	-
Università degli Studi di Udine	1	-
Università degli Studi e-Campus	1	-
Università degli Studi Guglielmo Marconi	2	-
Università del Salento	10	-
Università della Calabria	8	2
Università degli Studi di Cassino e del Lazio Meridionale	3	-
Università di Parma	2	-
Università di Pisa	10	-
Università di Trento	1	-
Università Politecnica delle Marche	1	-
Università degli Studi del Sannio di Benevento	1	-
Veritas SpA	1	-
VGA s.r.l.	1	-
	230	24

Latvia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Latvijas Universitāte	1	-
Rīgas Tehniskā Universitāte	2	-
	3	-

Lithuania

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Lietuvos energetikos institutas	2	-
Vilniaus Gedimino Technikos Universitetas (Vilnius Tech)	1	-
	3	-

Luxembourg

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology	7	-
Université du Luxembourg	1	-
	8	-

Malta

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
L-Università ta' Malta	4	1
The Foundation for Innovation and Research	-	1
	4	2

Mexico

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla	1	1
Centro de Innovación Aplicada en Tecnologías Competitivas	-	1

Research infrastructures cooperation for energy transition between European and Latin American and the Caribbean countries

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Centro de Investigación Científica de Yucatán	5	1
Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada	-	2
Centro de Investigación en Matemáticas, A.C.	-	1
Centro de Investigación en Materiales Avanzados	3	1
Centro de Investigación en Química Aplicada	-	2
Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados	3	1
Centro de Investigación y Desarrollo Tecnológico en Electroquímica S.C.	1	-
Centro de Investigaciones en Óptica, A.C.	1	-
El Colegio de Puebla, A.C.	1	-
Instituto Mexicano del Petróleo	1	-
Instituto Nacional de Electricidad y Energías limpias	2	-
Instituto Politécnico Nacional	8	2
Instituto Potosino de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica, A.C.	-	3
Tecnológico de Monterrey	3	5
Tecnológico Nacional de México	12	9
Universidad Autónoma de Baja California	2	1
Universidad Autónoma de Campeche	1	-
Universidad Autónoma de Chiapas	1	-
Universidad Autónoma de Ciudad Juárez	-	1
Universidad Autónoma de Coahuila	2	1
Universidad Autónoma de Guadalajara	-	1
Universidad Autónoma de Nayarit	1	-
Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León	3	15
Universidad Autónoma de Querétaro	5	-
Universidad Autónoma de San Luis Potosí	-	1
Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán	1	-
Universidad Autónoma de Zacatecas	-	2
Universidad Autónoma del Carmen	1	-
Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Hidalgo	-	1
Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México	1	1
Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos	3	-
Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Quintana Roo	1	-
Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana	4	8
Universidad de Ciencias y Artes de Chiapas	2	-
Universidad de Guadalajara	-	2
Universidad de Guanajuato	5	-
Universidad de Sonora	3	-
Universidad Tecnológica del Mayab	1	-
Universidad del Valle de México	1	-
Universidad Iberoamericana	1	-
Universidad Intercultural Indígena de Michoacán	1	-
Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco	1	-
Universidad Michoacana de San Nicolás de Hidalgo	3	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México	17	14
Universidad Panamericana	-	2
Universidad Politécnica de Aguascalientes	2	-
Universidad Politécnica de Guanajuato	1	-
Universidad Politécnica de San Luis Potosí	-	1
Universidad Politécnica de Victoria	2	-
Universidad Popular de la Chontalpa	1	-
Universidad Tecnológica de San Juan del Río	1	-
Universidad Veracruzana	1	3
	110	83

Netherlands

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Hogeschool Saxion	1	-
Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek (TNO)	6	-
Radboud Universiteit	3	-
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen	9	-
Technische Universiteit Delft	13	1
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven	6	-
Universiteit Leiden	2	-
Universiteit Twente	6	-
Universiteit Utrecht	4	1
Universiteit van Amsterdam	-	1
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	1	-
	51	3

Paraguay

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Parque Tecnológico Itaipu	1	-
	1	-

Peru

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú	-	3
Universidad Autónoma del Perú	-	1
Universidad César Vallejo	-	1
Universidad de Ingeniería y Tecnología	1	1
Universidad de Piura	1	-
Universidad Nacional Agraria La Molina	-	1
Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería	-	3
Universidad Nacional de San Agustín de Arequipa	-	3
Universidad Nacional Jorge Basadre Grohmann	-	1
Universidad Señor de Sipán	-	1
Universidad Tecnológica del Perú	-	1
	2	16

Poland

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Akademia Górniczo-Hutnicza im. Stanisława Staszica w Krakowie	14	-
Instytut Fizyki PAN	3	-
Instytut Gospodarki Surowcami Mineralnymi i Energią PAN	7	-
Lubelska Akademia WSEI	1	-
Łukasiewicz - Instytut Chemii Przemysłowej	1	-
Ministerstwo Klimatu i Środowiska	1	-
Politechnika Częstochowska	6	-
Politechnika Gdańska	7	-
Politechnika Koszalińska	1	-
Politechnika Krakowska im. Tadeusza Kościuszki	1	-
Politechnika Lubelska	2	-
Politechnika Opolska	2	-
Politechnika Poznańska	10	-
Politechnika Śląska	11	-
Politechnika Wrocławska	3	-
Sieć Badawcza Łukasiewicz	1	-
Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie	1	-
Uniwersytet Jana Długosza w Częstochowie	2	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Uniwersytet Mikołaja Kopernika w Toruniu	1	-
Uniwersytet Szczeciński	2	-
Uniwersytet Warszawski	4	-
Wojskowa Akademia Techniczna	3	-
	84	0

Portugal

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa	3	-
Instituto Politécnico do Porto	2	-
Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto	1	-
Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa	1	-
Instituto Universitário de Lisboa	-	1
International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory	2	-
Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia	1	-
Pólo de Inovação em Engenharia de Polímeros (PIEP)	2	-
Universidade de Aveiro	11	2
Universidade de Lisboa	1	-
Universidade do Minho	1	1
Universidade do Porto	10	1
Universidade Nova de Lisboa	1	2
	36	7

Romania

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Academia Româna	1	-
Institut de Physique des Matériaux, Bucarest-Magurele	1	-
Institutul Național de Cercetare-Dezvoltare pentru Tehnologii Criogenice și Izotopice Ramnicu Valcea	2	-
Universitatea Babeș-Bolyai	2	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universitatea de Stiinte Agricole si Medicina Veterinara din Cluj-Napoca	1	-
Universitatea Națională de Știință și Tehnologie POLITEHNICA București	1	-
Universitatea Tehnica din Cluj-Napoca	4	-
Universitatea Tehnică Gheorghe Asachi din Iași	2	-
	14	-

Slovakia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Národné superpočítačové centrum	1	-
Slovenská akadémia vied	1	-
Slovenská technická univerzita v Bratislave (STU)	3	-
Technická Univerzita v Košiciach	5	-
	10	-

Slovenia

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Institut "Jožef Stefan"	2	-
Kemijski inštitut	5	2
Univerza v Mariboru	1	-
	8	2

Spain

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Asociación de Servicios de Geología y Minería Iberoamericanos	-	2
Catalonia Institute for Energy Research IREC	3	2
Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas	2	-
Centro de Microanálisis de Materiales	-	1
Centro Ibérico de Investigación en Almacenamiento Energético	-	1
Centro Nacional de Hidrogeno (CNH2)	1	-
Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	10	1
Institución Catalana de Investigación y Estudios Avanzados	1	-
Institut de Ciències Fotoniques	1	-
Instituto Madrileño de Estudios Avanzados	3	-
Instituto Nicolás Cabrera	-	1
Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	2	-
Universidad Cardenal Herrera-CEU	5	-
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid	2	-
Universidad Complutense de Madrid	-	1
Universidad de Burgos	2	-
Universidad de Cádiz	8	-
Universidad de Cantabria	3	-
Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha	9	-
Universidad de Córdoba	1	2
Universidad de Extremadura	4	-
Universidad de Huelva	2	-
Universidad de Jaén	3	3
Universidad Autónoma de la Laguna	1	1
Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	1	-
Universidad de León	2	-
Universidad de Málaga	1	-
Universidad de Navarra	-	1
Universidad de Santiago de Compostela	3	-
Universidad de Sevilla	8	-
Universidad de Valladolid	6	3
Universidad de Zaragoza	1	1
Universidad del País Vasco	3	7
Universidad Loyola Andalucía	2	-
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	13	-
Universidad Pontificia Comillas	3	-
Universidad Rey Juan Carlos	1	-
Universidade de Vigo	1	-
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	1	-

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universitat d'Alacant	3	-
Universitat de Barcelona	2	3
Universitat de Girona	2	-
Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	3	-
Universitat Politècnica de València	2	5
Universitat Rovira i Virgili	-	1
	121	36

Sweden

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Chalmers tekniska högskola	7	-
Kungliga Tekniska högskolan	12	2
Linköpings universitet	7	-
Luleå tekniska universitet	4	-
Mälardalens universitet	1	-
RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB	1	-
Stockholms universitet	1	-
Uppsala universitet	8	5
	41	7

Uruguay

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universidad de la República	2	-
	2	-

Venezuela

Facility/Institute	Researchers identified per topic	
	Hydrogen	Lithium
Universidad Nacional Experimental del Táchira	1	-
	1	-

Energytran

Equipment

European Union

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Austria	BOKU University	Field emission environmental scanning electron microscope (FE-ESEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), small-angle X-ray scattering instrument (SAXS), wide-angle X-ray scattering instrument (WAXS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), nanoindentation equipment, optical microscopy tools, experimental chambers with controlled temperature and gas composition, equipment for hydropower studies.
Austria	Erich Schmid Institute of Materials Science	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), focused ion beam (FIB) system, electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) system, X-ray diffraction (XRD), nanoindentation equipment, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), sputtering systems for thin film deposition, optical microscopes, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) system.
Austria	Graz University of Technology	Mass spectroscopy (MS), Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS/MS, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Liquid Chromatography (LC) systems, ion chromatography, supercritical fluid chromatography, Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, combustion ion chromatography, microwave-assisted digestion systems, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.
Austria	Montanuniversität Leoben	X-ray scattering systems, potentiostats, X-ray diffraction (XRD), low-pressure adsorption equipment, high-pressure gravimetric adsorption equipment, horizontal tube furnace, laboratory workspace for production of flexible electrodes with roll press and PTFE binder.
Austria	Technische Universität Wien	Atomic layer deposition (ALD) system, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) system for graphene and carbon nanotubes, spin Coater, Accelerated Surface Area and Porosimetry System, High Resolution Micropore Analyzer, Catalyst Characterization Analyzer, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), gas chromatography (GC).
Belgium	Université Catholique de Louvain	Hand gloveboxes with integrated microscopes, hand plastic glovebox for wet synthesis under protective atmosphere, 3D printer, diffractometers with microfocusing Mo sources, TGA/DSC-MS, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, high-resolution mass spectrometers, surface area and porosity analyzer.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Belgium	Université de Mons	Mass spectroscopy (MS), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC), Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, TOC analyzer, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), optical imaging systems.
Belgium	Universiteit Gent	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, plasma diagnostics instruments for green hydrogen synthesis.
Belgium	Université Libre de Bruxelles	High-pressure hydrogen reactor, UV reactor, sublimation apparatus, tubular furnace, zone refiner for purification of organic semiconductors, gel permeation chromatography (GPC) setup, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), high-end optical microscope, UV-Vis spectroscopy, emission spectrometer, thermomicroscopy, spin-coater, X-ray diffraction (XRD), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), cyclic voltammetry equipment.
Belgium	Vrije Universiteit Brussel	High-resolution mass spectrometer (HRMS), time-of-flight mass spectrometer (ToF-MS), ion mobility spectrometry mass spectrometer (IMS-MS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), differential thermal analysis system (DTA), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), thermomechanical analyzer (TMA), Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Auger electron spectrometer (AES), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), scanning probe microscope (SPM), scanning electrochemical microscope (SECM), fluorescence spectrometer, gas adsorption porosimeter, dynamic light scattering particle size analyzer (DLS).
Czechia	Brno University of Technology	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, microwave-assisted organic synthesis system, characterization instruments, equipment for the synthesis of organic, hybrid, and biohybrid materials, instruments for photocatalytic hydrogen production, facilities for the development of organic semiconductors and hybrid perovskite systems, tools for the design and preparation of materials for sustainable energy applications.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Czechia	Czech Technical University in Prague	X-ray fluorescence (XRF), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), elemental analyzer CHNS/O, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), confocal Raman microscope, transmission electron microscope (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), particle size analyzer, C/N analyzer, TQ-XS mass spectrometer, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), Gas chromatography (GC), photoelectric spectrometer, and photocatalytic reactors for gas-phase analysis.
Czechia	J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, EPR spectrometer, mass spectroscopy (MS), UV-Vis/Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), electrochemical instrumentation, confocal fluorescence microscopes, selected ion flow tube mass spectrometry (SIFT-MS), secondary electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (SESI-MS), chemical synthesis lab for organic synthesis and chemical modifications of materials, electronic spectroscopy setup for characterization of 2D materials.
Czechia	Masaryk University	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), fluorescence spectroscopy systems, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), differential thermal analysis (DTA) system, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), scanning probe microscope (SPM), fluorescence spectrometer, gas adsorption porosimetry system, dynamic light scattering (DLS) particle size analyzer, selected ion flow tube mass spectrometer (SIFT-MS), secondary electrospray ionization mass spectrometer (SESI-MS), electronic spectroscopy setup for 2D materials characterization.
Czechia	Akademie věd České republiky	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), X-ray diffraction (XRD), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) system, nanoindentation tester, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM), superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer, Hall effect measurement system, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), gas adsorption analyzer (BET), dynamic light scattering (DLS) particle size analyzer, potentiostat/galvanostat, plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) system.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Cyprus	University of Cyprus	Furnaces with atmosphere and gas flow control, SURFACE HV deposition chamber with Reflection High-Energy Electron Diffraction (RHEED), laser systems, Hummer reactive sputtering system, sputter coater, mask aligner, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Quantum Design Physical Properties Measurement System, DC and pulsed I-V measurement system with micropositioners and digital microscope, custom-made electrospinning setup with four-channel volumetric microdialysis pump, grounded target collector within Faraday enclosure, spin-coater, UV-Vis spectroscopy, size exclusion chromatography system, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), multi-angle dynamic and static light scattering systems, glove box, high vacuum line, equipment for solid-state reactions and mechanical alloying.
Denmark	Aalborg University	Thin film deposition and characterization systems, nanoscale material synthesis equipment, metamaterial fabrication tools for solar cells, high-temperature material synthesis for thermophotovoltaics, wide-bandgap semiconductor processing tools, piezoelectric nanostructure synthesis equipment, polymer and composite material synthesis and testing instruments, semiconductor nanoparticle synthesis for photocatalysis and solar cells, electrochemical reactors for inorganic composite production, inorganic polymer building material synthesis, equipment for study and production of disordered materials, experimental and computational tools for energy storage materials, hydrogen production and utilization reactors, electrochemical and thermochemical reactor systems for hydrogen and electro-fuels.
Denmark	Aarhus Universitet	Advanced surface science tools for catalyst analysis, synthesis equipment for BiOX nanomaterials (X = Cl, Br, I), energy storage and conversion material testing systems, hydrothermal processing equipment, membrane fabrication and engineering tools, electrochemical energy conversion systems, intelligent advanced material synthesis equipment, hydrogen storage synthesis systems using boron chemistry.
Denmark	Technical University of Denmark	Physical Vapour Deposition (PVD) chamber, atomic layer deposition (ALD) system, Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) system with in-situ Reflection High-Energy Electron Diffraction (RHEED), ceramic 3D printer, slot die coater, vacuum furnaces, spin coater, climate chamber, UV encapsulation tools, solar simulation box, light-optical microscope, electron microscope (with EDX), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), optical emission spectrometer (OES), DSC-TGA system, electromechanical test machines, scanning electron microscope (SEM), additive manufacturing equipment for fiber composites, infrastructure for renewable energy systems, X-ray and neutron imaging systems (3D Imaging Centre), chemical pilot plant for process development.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Finland	LUT University	Microbeam X-ray diffractometer, high-resolution X-ray diffractometer, polarized light microscopes, electromagnets, scanning electron microscope (SEM), atomic/magnetic force microscope (AFM/MFM), magneto-mechanical testing devices, Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), flow reactors, custom-built femtosecond pulse laser ablation setup, potentiostats/galvanostats, gas adsorption analyzers (BET), dynamic light scattering (DLS) particle size analyzers, glove boxes, high vacuum lines, equipment for solid-state reactions, mechanical alloying tools.
Finland	Aalto University	X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscopes (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, potentiostats/galvanostats, glove boxes, high vacuum lines, equipment for solid-state reactions, mechanical alloying tools, various deposition systems including atomic layer deposition (ALD) system and chemical vapor deposition (CVD).
France	CNRS Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	Micro- and nanofabrication equipment, rechargeable battery research platforms, supercapacitor testing systems, photovoltaic testing facilities, microsystems fabrication tools, microfluidic devices, unconventional microfabrication systems, solid/liquid interface characterization instruments, nanoparticle synthesis systems, composite material processing tools, porous material synthesis equipment, signal processing tools, data processing systems, high-performance computing resources.
France	ENSTA Bretagne	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), TriboIndenter, potentiostat for corrosion testing, laser.
France	IFP Energies nouvelles	Microfluidics laboratory tests, elemental analysis laboratory, X-ray scanner for homogeneity characterization, laboratories for morphology and mechanical properties characterization of solids, GC- Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, beamline at Synchrotron for high-resolution 3D X-ray imaging, micro- and nanotomography stations, high-speed tomography scanning equipment, high-pressure and temperature vessels, single-cylinder test cells, high-performance computing platform.
France	Université de Lorraine	High-field nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), ion chromatography system, mineralization equipment, MP analyzer, laser ablation system, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, micro-XRF analyzer, ion probe for microscopic scale elemental and isotopic analysis, microcalorimeter, light scattering instruments, liquid chromatography systems, X-ray crystallography equipment, numerical wattmeters.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
France	Institut de Chimie et des Matériaux de Paris Est (ICMPE) - UMR7182	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Electron Probe Micro-Analysis (EPMA), Optical Microscopy, Characterization of Hydrides, Characterization of Mechanical Properties, Electrochemical Characterization, Mercury Porosimetry, Physical Characterization (Magnetic Properties and Electronic Transport), gas adsorption analyzers (BET), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Thermal Analysis (DSC, DTA, and TGA), Centrifugal Partition Chromatography (CPC), Flash Chromatography, Gas chromatography (GC), Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Liquid Chromatography-MS.
France	Arts et Métiers	Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) system, sputtering systems, low pressure thermochemical ovens, Spark spectrometer, Microanalysis X (EDX and WDS), scanning electron microscope (SEM).
France	Université Grenoble Alpes	High-field nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-AES, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), ion chromatography systems, mineralization equipment, thermostated leaching/precipitation reactors, laser ablation systems, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS or time-of-flight (TOF) mass spectrometers, micro-XRF analyzers, scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscopes (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), fluorescence macroscopes, Nanodrop spectrophotometers.
Germany	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon GmbH	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), light-optical microscope, Raman spectroscopy, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), UV-photo emission (UPS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), secondary ions mass spectrometry (SIMS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Transmission and Glancing Angle microscopy, Laser scanning microscope, Glow Discharge Optical Emission Spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Particle size analyzers, metallurgical microscopes.
Germany	Helmholtz-Institut Ulm	Energy Storage, battery production, electrochemical materials (not details available).
Germany	Karlsruher Institut für Technologie	Energy lab (not details available).

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Germany	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR)	Battery lab, Furnaces, Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) systems, Thermoelectric generator, Energy storage, Tape-Laying Machine (fiber-composite structures), Solar simulator, solar furnace, scanning electron microscope (SEM), research power plant.
Germany	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen	Energy storage, wind energy converters, solar installations, electrochemical energy storage.
Germany	Technische Universität Clausthal	Flash differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Heating microscope, high temperature furnaces, Laser flash apparatus (LFA), Thermal analysis, mass spectroscopy (MS), Thermogravimetry, Digital laser scanning microscope, Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, scanning electron microscope (SEM), UV/Vis spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF).
Germany	Technische Universität München	TOC analyzer, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Ion chromatography, photometers, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, Gas chromatography (GC).
Germany	Technische Universität Berlin	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Electron beam microprobe (ESMA), light microscopy (LIM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM).
Germany	Universität Bayreuth	Polymeric materials analysis, Flash column chromatography, microwave synthesizer, Aqueous size-exclusion chromatography, Gas chromatography (GC).
Germany	Universität Stuttgart	Field-Ion Microscope, Laser pulsing systems, Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) system, Glove boxes for preparation of electrochemical cells, Potentiostates, optical reflectometry, Tomographic Atom Probe (TAP), Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD).
Germany	Fraunhofer Institute	High-vacuum evaporation systems (ion-assisted electron beam evaporation, thermal boat evaporation), Magnetron sputtering systems, atomic layer deposition (ALD) system, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), measurement techniques for testing long-term stability and adhesion of optical coatings, climate testing microscope with image processing, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV/Vis Spectroscopy, UV/VIS/NIR-spectrometer.
Germany	Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH	Electrocatalytic interface, chemical hydrogen storage, composite membrane design, autothermal LOHC-Dehydrogenation, polymer synthesis, solar cells.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Germany	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Electrochemical deposition, Conductivity, physisorption equipment, Macropores measurement with mercury, Gas chromatography (GC), Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Sorption analyzer.
Germany	Universität Würzburg	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Mercury Porosimetry, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Spincoater.
Greece	National Centre for Scientific Research "DEMOKRITOS"	Hydrothermal synthesis systems, sol-gel processing equipment, pyrolytic synthesis apparatus, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) systems, atomic layer deposition (ALD) systems, Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) systems, laser ablation equipment, sputtering systems, molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) systems, transmission electron microscopes (TEM), high-resolution scanning/transmission electron microscopes (HR-S/TEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) systems, energy-filtered transmission electron microscope (EFTEM) equipment, solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, thermal analysis instruments, particle size analyzers, stable isotope analysis equipment, chromatography/mass spectrometry systems, environmental simulation chambers, photovoltaic and optoelectronic device fabrication tools, nanolithography systems, plasma processing equipment, and synchrotron X-ray and neutron scattering instruments.
Greece	Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas	Bench-scale catalytic reactors, pilot-scale catalytic reactors, fluid catalytic cracking (FCC) pilot plant, hydroprocessing units, catalytic pyrolysis units, catalyst synthesis facilities, catalyst characterization instruments, catalyst deactivation analysis systems, catalyst regeneration equipment, selective catalytic reduction (SCR) systems, DeSOx units, analytical laboratories for fuel and biofuel characterization.
Greece	University of Crete	TOC analyzer, Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, ionic chromatography system, UV-Vis spectroscopy, electrical conductivity meters.
Greece	University of Thessaly	Ceramic material synthesis equipment, geopolymer production systems, structural ceramics characterization instruments, composite materials evaluation tools, nanomaterials testing systems, greenhouse climate control equipment, renewable energy systems for agricultural applications.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Greece	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	Stirling cogeneration engine, thermal energy storage installation with PCM and nanofluids, exhaust gas analyzer, gas flow analyzer, electrical power meter, sensors and instruments for monitoring solar energy systems, electrochemical synthesis and characterization equipment for metallic, semiconductive, and composite materials, electrolytic deposition setups, electrochemical analysis instruments (voltammetry, chronoamperometry), photocurrent spectroscopy, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), photoelectrochemical device development tools, optical microscopy, thermal analysis instruments, mercury intrusion porosimetry, non-destructive testing equipment (infrared thermography, ultrasound pulse velocity, georadar, portable digital microscopy), ageing chambers (salt spray, UV, thermal cycles, atmospheric pollution simulation), dielectric spectroscopy equipment, ultra-high vacuum (UHV) setup with quadrupole mass spectrometer, electrolytic deposition equipment for polycrystalline semiconductor films, high vacuum systems with metal sublimator, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), ultrasonic reactor, microwave reactor, polymerization reactors, solid state polymerization reactor, thermoforming equipment, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Gas chromatography (GC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA)
Greece	University of Patras	Gas adsorption analyzer (BET), UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, scanning electron microscope (SEM) with EDX, transmission electron microscope (TEM), ultraviolet photoelectron spectrometer (UPS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Gas chromatography (GC), Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, transient mass spectrometry (transient-MS), DRIFTS with transient capabilities, polymer synthesis reactors, hybrid nanomaterial synthesis equipment, Li-ion battery materials development tools, structural analysis instruments, thermal analysis instruments, electrical and magnetic property analyzers, morphology analyzers, chemical property analyzers, nanomaterials characterization systems.
Ireland	Dublin City University	Low temperature photoluminescence and reflectance in near UV, visible and near Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), high field superconducting magnet and uniaxial stress apparatus, vapor phase and chemical bath growth techniques and annealing furnaces, Hall Effect measurement apparatus, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), secondary ion mass spectroscopy (SIMS), electrical probe station and Semiconductor Characterization System, Scanning Tunnelling Microscope, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Scanning electron microscopy and cathodoluminescence, field emission scanning electron microscopy and scanning transmission electron microscopy.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Ireland	University College Cork	Mass spectroscopy (MS), scanning electron microscopes (SEM), Raman FT-IR system, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight, Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), transmission electron microscope (TEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), facilities for synthesis of noble metal nanoparticles and oxide-supported nanostructures.
Ireland	University College Dublin	Scanning electron microscopes (SEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), sputtering/coating systems, elemental analyzers, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), differential scanning calorimeters (DSC), digital image correlation (DIC) systems, plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) systems, magnetron sputtering systems, atmospheric plasma systems, powder coating systems, particle size analyzers, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, laser ablation systems, thermal ionization mass spectrometers.
Ireland	University of Limerick	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscopes (SEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), differential scanning calorimeters (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzers (TGA), potentiostats/galvanostats, glove boxes, high vacuum lines, equipment for solid-state reactions, atomic layer deposition (ALD) system, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) systems.
Italy	Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna	UV-Vis spectroscopy-near Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), stopped-flow instrument for reaction kinetics studies via absorption and emission spectroscopy, microscopy, electrochemical equipment for cyclic voltammetry, differential-pulsed voltammetry, chronoamperometry, coulometry with conventional and ultramicroelectrodes, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), absorption and emission Spectro electrochemistry setup, Zeta potential analyzer, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM).
Italy	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	Chemical laboratories equipped for solid-state reactions and chemical characterization, rolling and drawing machines to produce superconducting wires and tapes, furnaces with controlled atmospheres, printers for low-cost material deposition, DC sputtering system, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Scanning tunneling microscope (STM).
Italy	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale	Gas chromatography (GC), High-pressure and high-temperature geophysical testing facilities, Analytical instruments for CO ₂ and gas monitoring, Optical microscopy systems.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Italy	ENEA Centro Ricerche Casaccia	X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy-NIR spectrophotometer, transient absorption and emission spectroscopy, hydrothermal synthesis autoclave, stopped-flow instrument for reaction kinetics studies, confocal microscope, electrochemical equipment for cyclic voltammetry, differential-pulsed voltammetry, chronoamperometry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Zeta potential analyzer.
Italy	Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia	Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), microscopes, equipment for the thermal characterization of composite materials, optical spectroscopy instruments, Field Flow Fractionation, electromagnet, electrospinning, spray coating, rod coaters, thermal extruder, 3-D printer, micro-machining equipment.
Italy	Istituto Di Tecnologie Avanzate Per L'energia, Messina	Continuous-flow reactors, Autoclave reactors, Automatic spray coater, deposition systems, potentiostat/galvanostat, electrolysis test station, Cartesian robot for 3D printing of catalytic pastes, hydraulic press for catalyst pellet preparation, Laboratory-scale test plants for Autothermal Reforming (ATR), Oxy Steam Reforming (OSR), Tri-Reforming (TR), and Steam Reforming processes, Fixed-bed reactors, Gas chromatography (GC) and GC-MS, optical microscope, hydrogenation reactors for methanation and ammonia synthesis, supercritical water gasification system, TOC analyzer, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), PEM test stations for single cells and short stacks, Electrolyzers, Biomass gasifiers and syngas purification lines, Hydrogen or syngas generators based on reforming processes, Cogeneration and trigeneration systems, Hydrogen storage systems, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Italy	Politecnico di Bari	Thin-film deposition system, clean room with chemical hood, cryogenic and dismantling techniques for photovoltaic panel recycling, measurement of thermal diffusivity, specific heat and thermal conductivity, metallographic preparation equipment, optical microscopy for microstructure evaluation, tools for modeling, design, simulation, fabrication and characterization of optoelectronic, photonic and nanoelectronic components.
Italy	Politecnico di Milano	Clean room for creating device prototypes integrating different technologies (photonics, micro and nano electronics, spintronics, micro mechanics), microfabrication (plasma-enhanced chemical vapor depositions, sputtering) and nanofabrication (electronic lithography, nano-imprinting, AFRM nanolithography), nano-indentation system, TEM microscope.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Italy	Università degli Studi di Brescia	Photolithography system for thick film mask fabrication, photonic sintering system, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Infrared (IR) spectroscopy-TGA.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Firenze	Corrosion testing equipment, metallographic analysis tools, X-ray diffraction (XRD), surface engineering equipment, heat treatment furnaces.
Italy	Università degli Studi dell'Aquila	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Gas chromatography (GC), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Nitrogen porosimeter, Infrared spectroscopy (IR), Differential Thermal Analysis system, Chamber furnace, Tubular furnace, Ion chromatography, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Optical microscope.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Multirays photochemical reactor with interchangeable lamps, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Liquid crystal thermography (TLC) system, Optical methods including holographic interferometry, Radiator test bench, Prototype lithium bromide absorption refrigerator with performance monitoring system.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Genova	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), transmission electron microscope (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Calorimetric measurement systems, Atomic spectrometry instruments, Multi-collector ICP-MS, Sol-gel synthesis apparatus, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Synthesis apparatus for cathode and anode materials, Sintering furnaces for electrolytes, Facilities for producing engineered electrodes, Equipment for studying electrochemical kinetics at electrodes.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Cagliari	Energy characterization of solar-based systems, ion chromatography, Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, elemental analysis of CHN, TOC analyzer.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia	Scanning tunneling microscope (STM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), High-Resolution Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (HREELS), facilities for the synthesis and characterization of semiconductor nanowires, 2D materials, and (poly)electrolytes, Equipment for developing and testing innovative nanodevice architectures.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Italy	Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	Spectroscopy instruments, microscopy equipment, structural characterization tools, facilities for the synthesis and characterization of amorphous and nanostructured materials, both inorganic and hybrid, including sol-gel synthesis apparatus, thermal analysis instruments.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Padova	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Near-Infrared (NIR) absorption spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Scanning tunneling microscope (STM), Electron Spectroscopies, Operando techniques (EC-STM, EXAFS), UV-Vis spectroscopy-NIR absorption and emission spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Liquid Chromatography-MS, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Optical Microscopy, Spectroelectrochemical setups, Raman spectroscopy.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Palermo	3D printer, ultrasonic transducers for composite materials, laser profilometer for surface texture analysis, Nd:YAG pulsed laser deposition (PLD) system, CO ₂ laser-assisted thermal evaporation system, high-temperature oven, scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), and cleanroom facilities for microfabrication.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Pavia	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, high-resolution mass spectrometer UHPLC-HRMS/MS, STED microscope, metal 3D printer.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Salerno	X-ray diffraction (XRD), Infrared and VCD Spectroscopy, Mass spectroscopy (MS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Thermal analysis equipment, Chromatography equipment, Synthesis and Characterization of Nanomaterials (carbon nanotubes, coated nanoparticles, graphene), Development of cathodes for electrochemical devices.
Italy	Università degli Studi di Sassari	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Elemental analyzer CHN, Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Liquid Chromatography Coupled with High Resolution Mass Spectrometer UPLC - HRMS, Liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometer - UPLC - MS, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, Raman Spectroscopy, Portable X-ray fluorescence (XRF), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM).
Italy	Università degli Studi di Torino	UV-Vis spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, Potentiostat, microwave synthesizer, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, UHPLC-HRMS spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, X-ray diffraction (XRD).
Italy	Università del Salento	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Furnaces Optical microscopy.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Italy	Università di Pisa	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) coupled to a microscope, liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry detector.
Italy	Università della Calabria	Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) system, Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) system, sol-gel processing systems, hydrothermal reactors, spin coaters, plasma-enhanced deposition systems, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM).
Netherlands	Delft University of Technology	Polymer tapeline machine, physical characterization instruments, equipment for synthetic fuel production and consumption, energy technology and storage systems, process intensification and multiphase system apparatus.
Netherlands	Nederlandse Organisatie voor toegepast natuurwetenschappelijk onderzoek- TNO	Chemical reactors for lab- and pilot-scale preparation of colloidal dispersions, pilot lines for functional glass coatings and polymer films, lab and pilot-scale equipment for polymer processing and recycling, experimental facilities for chemical, thermal and mechanical characterization of energetic materials, test installations for absorption and adsorption processes in CO ₂ capture, pilot installations for converting CO ₂ into chemical building materials or renewable fuels, facilities for developing and optimizing process technologies for biofuel production, equipment for electrochemical conversion of CO ₂ to ethylene.
Netherlands	Rijksuniversiteit Groningen	UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Raman spectroelectrochemistry systems, bipotentiostat, rotating disk electrode, Raman spectroscopy-microscopy systems, nanosecond time-resolved spectroscopy (absorption, emission, Raman), NIR absorption and emission spectroscopy instruments, 3D printer, transient absorption spectrometer, wall sheet photoreactor, UPLC-MS, TLC-MS, Atomic Force Microscopy (ATM), fluorescence microscopes, super-resolution microscopes, optical microscopes, Raman microscope, scanning electron microscope (SEM), differential scanning calorimeter, calorimeter, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).
Netherlands	Technische Universiteit Eindhoven	3D printing farm, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), microwave plasma atomic emission spectrometer, magnetron sputtering tool, atomic layer deposition (ALD) system, high-resolution microscopy systems, surface analysis systems, microreactors, small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) equipment, optical microscopy tools, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Netherlands	Universiteit Twente	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), 3D printers, energy impact and fatigue analyzers, differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), Raman spectroscopy, nanosecond time-resolved absorption and emission spectroscopy, NIR absorption and emission spectroscopy, transient absorption spectroscopy, photo flow reactor, UPLC-MS, TLC-MS, fluorescence microscopes, super-resolution microscopes, Raman microscope, calorimeters, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).
Netherlands	Universiteit Utrecht	Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Gas chromatography (GC), liquid chromatography system, cyclic voltammetry setup for electrochemical analysis.
Netherlands	Universiteit Leiden	UV-Vis spectroscopy, Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), Raman spectroscopy/microscopy systems, nanosecond time-resolved spectroscopy (absorption, emission, Raman), NIR absorption and emission spectroscopy instruments, 3D printer, transient absorption spectrometer, wall sheet photoreactor, photo flow reactor, UPLC-MS, TLC-MS, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), super-resolution microscopes, optical microscopes, scanning electron microscope (SEM), calorimeters, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).
Poland	AGH University of Krakow	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Gas chromatography (GC), mass spectroscopy (MS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, potentiostat/galvanostat, solar simulator, glove box, spin coater, sputtering system, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) system, tube furnace, high-pressure reactor.
Poland	Częstochowa University Of Technology	Surface area and porosity analyzer, fully stirred reactors, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, gas sorption analyzer.
Poland	Institute of Physics of the Polish Academy of Sciences	X-ray/UV photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS/UPS), High resolution transmission electron microscope, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy.
Poland	Opole University of Technology	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-OES, Microwave digestion system, Photovoltaic installation test stands.
Poland	Politechnika Wrocławska	3D printer, Surface area analyzer, particle size analyzers, Zeta potential analyzer, Laser diffraction particle size analyzer, Optical microscope, Fluorescence microscope, Automatic polarimeter, UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Poland	Institute of the Polish Academy of Sciences	Chromatography systems, equipment for catalytic tests, apparatus for electrochemical measurements, surface area and pore size analyzers capable of physisorption and chemisorption, thermal analysis and calorimetric equipment, equipment for structural analysis, ultra-high-vacuum systems for surface science analysis, microscopes, equipment for surface nanostructures and thin films analysis, equipment for nano and micro-objects analysis, equipment for theoretical calculations.
Poland	Silesian University of Technology	Automated graphitization equipment, Manual tube cracker for CO ₂ introduction, Vacuum line for carbonate decomposition and CO ₂ purification, spectrometer for ¹⁴ C measurement, vacuum lines for sample combustion and conversion to benzene, Oxygen-flow line with two-zone oven, Infra-red oven, elemental analyzer.
Poland	University of Warsaw	NAP-XPS Surface Analysis System, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) System, Gas Chromatography (GC)-MS, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray Fluorescence (XRF), Raman Spectroscopy.
Portugal	Universidade de Aveiro	Laser systems, near-field scanning optical microscope (NSOM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), absorption/transmission spectroscopy systems (VUV, UV, VIS, IR), photoluminescence (PL) and PL excitation (PLE) systems, photoconductivity (PC) measurement system, Raman spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), UV-Vis spectrometer, Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectrometer, continuous flow cryostats, ferromagnetic resonance (FMR) measurement capability, electrical (impedance) and magnetoelectric measurements.
Portugal	Universidade do Porto	Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), supercritical HPLC, pressure swing adsorption (PSA) units, electric swing adsorption (ESA) unit, ultra-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC/MS-MS), 3D printing equipment, laser systems.
Portugal	Instituto Politécnico do Porto	UV-Vis spectroscopy, Infrared Spectroscopy (IR), Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscopes (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), differential scanning calorimeters (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzers (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), 3D printers.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Portugal	Universidade Nova de Lisboa	X-ray diffraction (XRD), fluorescence microarray scanner, UV-Vis spectroscopy, bioelectrochemistry setups, UltraFlex mass spectrometer, Gas chromatography (GC)-MS and Liquid Chromatography (LC)-MS, Atomic Force Microscopy (ATM), surface-enhanced resonance Raman (SERR), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray crystallography, dynamic light scattering (DLS) with zeta potential analysis, spectroelectrochemistry, and crystallization, sol-gel ceramic powder production systems, polymer-ceramic composite film fabrication tools, thermal evaporation metallization apparatus.
Portugal	Politécnico de Lisboa	UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscopes (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), differential scanning calorimeters (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzers (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), electrochemical workstations, 3D printers.
Portugal	International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), (Thin) film deposition and material growth, advanced optical microscopy, nanoparticle analysis, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (TGA/DSC), optical emission spectrometry, gas adsorption analyzer (BET), and material testing instruments.
Portugal	Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia	Solar thermal systems, pyranometer calibration equipment, solar storage testing apparatus, outdoor raceway bioreactors, photobioreactors, electroflocculator, thermogravimetric analyzer (TG/DTA), electrochemical testing systems for corrosion analysis, surface treatment equipment for metallic coatings, artificial and natural aging test chambers, analytical instruments for chemical characterization of materials and coatings, equipment for physical characterization of materials and coatings, testing apparatus for organic/polymeric coatings.
Portugal	Universidade do Minho	Power electronics for energy systems, renewable energy grid interfaces, battery charging systems, power electronics for electric and hybrid vehicles, micro and nano energy harvesting devices, smart materials for energy applications, energy-aware software development, energy efficiency in buildings, environmental and energy technologies, biotechnological processes for energy applications, polymeric materials for energy storage and conversion.
Spain	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	Potentiostats, Galvanostats, low temperature ovens, plasma etching, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Spain	Universidad de Cádiz	Physisorption equipment, X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Vis spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, ultrasonic probe, mercury intrusion porosimetry, water vapor permeability, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), optical microscope, scanning electron microscope (SEM), Transmission electron microscope (TEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.
Spain	Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha	X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-Ray Reflectivity, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), scanning electron microscope (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Raman spectroscopy, Z-Potential, mass spectroscopy (MS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Magnetic Measurements, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Surface analyzer.
Spain	Catalonia Institute for Energy Research IREC	Solar simulators, potentiostats, photocatalytic reactors and electrochemical cells, electrode and catalyst fabrication, Glove box for battery assembly and electrochemical testing, potentiostats, furnaces for battery testing, UV-Vis spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, Gas chromatography (GC), Battery/fuel cell analysis systems, sputtering, chemical vapor deposition (CVD) system.
Spain	Universidad de Extremadura	Surface analyzer, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Time of Flight (TOF)-secondary ions mass spectroscopy (SIMS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray reflectometry, Mercury Porosimetry, physisorption equipment, Simultaneous thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), X-ray fluorescence (XRF).
Spain	Universidad de Jaén	Gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, mass spectroscopy (MS), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.
Spain	Universidad del País Vasco	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Magnetic susceptibility measurement systems, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Spain	Universidad de Sevilla	Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Specific heat capacity analyzer, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Magnetic moment measurement, Magnetic susceptibility measurement, Electrical conductivity measurement, Mercury Porosimetry, physisorption equipment, chemisorption equipment, Laser diffraction, Zeta potential analyzer, high-temperature material treatment equipment, transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Focused ion beam microscope (FIB), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Scanning tunneling microscope (STM), inorganic sample preparation equipment, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Total reflection X-ray fluorescence (TXRF), Portable Raman spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS.
Spain	Universidad de Valladolid	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Super-resolution microscope, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Gas chromatography (GC), Ion chromatography, Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC), Thermal and mechanical property analyzers for polymers, Polymer synthesis reactors, synthesis equipment for functional materials, Electrospinning system for polymer fiber fabrication.
Spain	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Thermal conductivity analyzers, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), optical microscope, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).
Spain	Universitat Politècnica de València	X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Transmission electron microscope (TEM), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), optical microscope.
Spain	Instituto IMDEA Energía	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS), Thermal Desorption Spectroscopy (TDS)-MS, high vacuum magnetron sputtering system, ultra-high vacuum molecular beam epitaxy system.
Spain	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela	Mass spectroscopy (MS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, magnetic susceptibility equipment, Microscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, furnaces.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Spain	Universitat d'Alacant	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Ion chromatography, Mercury porosimeter, Differential thermal analyzer, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), Elemental analyzer for CHNS, Pilot-scale reactors, Pilot plant for chemical processes, Pilot-scale polymer processing equipment.
Spain	Universitat de Barcelona	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Ion chromatography, gas adsorption analyzer (BET), Differential thermal analyzer, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Micro X-ray fluorescence (μ FRX), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), Elemental analyzer.
Spain	Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas	Anoxic gloveboxes, scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Elemental analyzer.
Spain	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) systems, physical vapor deposition systems, Sol-gel processing equipment, electrochemical deposition setups, spin coating machines, sputtering systems, Molecular beam epitaxy systems, high-temperature furnaces, hydrothermal synthesis reactors, X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Photoluminescence spectrometers, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Time of Flight (TOF)-secondary ions mass spectroscopy (SIMS), Solar simulator systems, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Cyclic voltammetry (CV) equipment, Current-voltage characterization systems.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Spain	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Focused ion beam microscope (FIB), scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Confocal Raman microscope, Infrared (IR) spectrometer, UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Magnetic coercivity measurement equipment, furnaces.
Spain	Universidad Pontificia Comillas	Polymer synthesis equipment, composite material fabrication equipment, microscope equipment for microstructural analysis, Thermal analysis instruments, Electrical conductivity measurement devices, Magnetic property measurement instruments.
Spain	Universidad de Cantabria	X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Atomic absorption spectroscopy.
Sweden	Uppsala Universitet	X-ray diffractometers (XRD), high-temperature furnaces for ceramic and metallic synthesis, potentiostats/galvanostats, compact mass spectrometer, portable Raman spectroscopy systems, scanning electron microscope (SEM), magnetic and gravimetric equipment.
Sweden	Chalmers University of Technology	Electron beam lithography systems, metal and insulating thin film deposition systems (evaporation and sputtering), furnaces, mass spectroscopy (MS), FT-ICR mass spectrometer, UHPLC-MS/MS equipment, gas chromatography (GC)-MS, UHPLC systems, electron microscopes, X-ray diffraction (XRD), optical microscopes, Mass spectroscopy (MS).
Sweden	Linköpings Universitet	Chemical reactors, rotating disk electrode setup, electrochemical flow cells for electrolyzers, redox flow battery cells, fuel cells, H ₂ and O ₂ gas humidity system for fuel cells, electronic load, H ₂ electrolyzers, high power source for electrolyzers, permeability meter coupled to Mass spectroscopy (MS), glove box for alkali metal batteries, solid-state coin cell battery line, electrochemical potentiostats and bi-potentiostat, thermogalvanic setup, high-temperature oven, vacuum oven, desktop ¹³ C and ¹ H-NMR, optical absorption spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimeter, thermogravimetry equipment, particle size analyzer.
Sweden	Luleå University of Technology	3D imaging system, Diffraction Contrast Tomography for 3D crystallographic imaging, gas chromatography (GC), UV-Vis spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), UHPLC and HPLC systems, ion chromatography system, fluorescence microscope, single-shot pyrolyzer.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Sweden	The Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)	Time-resolved angle-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy system, ultrafast electron microscope, terahertz time-domain spectroscopy system, nonlinear optical structures in ferroelectrics and semiconductors, laser processing and 3D-printing equipment for glass structures, optical fiber and sensor fabrication systems, solid-state and fiber laser construction tools, optical spectrum analyzers, laser equipment, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

Latin America and Caribbean

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Argentina	Universidad de Buenos Aires	Pilot plant for the production and purification of hydrogen, elemental analysis CHSNO, trace chemical analysis by FIA, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Ion Chromatography, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas adsorption analyzer (BET), Density and electrical conductivity determinations, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Luminescence and fluorescence spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, UV-visible spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Polarization optical microscopy.
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de la Plata	Prototype hydrogen generation system, electrolyzer, Li-ion battery prototypes, electrocatalyst synthesis and characterization equipment.
Argentina	Universidad Tecnológica Nacional	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Microwave digester, Ion chromatography, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), 3D thermal printer, Equipment for gas chemisorption and physisorption analysis, Stirred and heated batch reactor, scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de Cuyo	Chemical reactor, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), ion chromatography, gas chromatography (GC), Atomic absorption spectroscopy.
Argentina	Comision Nacional de Energía Atómica	Hydrogen adsorption and desorption equipment in materials, reactors, hydrogen thermal compression systems, equipment for the capture, purification and compression of H ₂ , PEM fuel cell testing stations, inkjet system, glove box, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), electrochemical differential mass spectrometer, potentiostats/galvanostats, tube furnace, heated presses.
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de Córdoba	Electrolyzer, electrochemical cells, Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), glove box, potentiostat/galvanostat, tube furnace, vacuum furnace, UV-Vis spectroscopy, lithium metal thickness regulator.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de Jujuy	Button cell assembler, Vacuum oven, Glove box, multipotentiostat/galvanostat, Rotating electrode, battery cyclers, scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA).
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de Catamarca	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD).
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de Salta	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Optical Microscope with Polarization, Epifluorescence, Microthermometry, Cathodoluminescence, Membrane Electrolyzer.
Argentina	Universidad Nacional de Santiago del Estero	Ion trap mass spectrometer, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), Inverted Fluorescence Microscope, scanning electron microscope (SEM), Raman Spectroscopy-coupled Microscope, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Spectrofluorometer, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), potentiostat-galvanostat, Fiber Optic Spectrophotometer, 3D printers.
Argentina	Servicio Geologico Minero Argentino	Atomic absorption spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Ion Chromatography, scanning electron microscope (SEM), instruments and equipment for: preparation of thin sections and intaglio specimens.
Argentina	Asociación Argentina del Hidrógeno	Experimental hydrogen plant, electrolyzer, high-sensitivity hydrogen sensors.
Argentina	Universidad Nacional del Sur	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Scanning Spectrofluorometer, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Inverted Fluorescence Microscope, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Elemental Analyzer, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), gas chromatography (GC), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Microwave Equipment, Potentiostat.
Argentina	Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Multi-technique Surface Analysis System, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, gas chromatography (GC)-MS, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), heat treatment equipment, microwave oven, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Raman spectroscopy.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Brazil	Centro Nacional de Pesquisa em Energia e Materiais	Electrolyzer, scanning electron microscope (SEM), nanofabrication equipment, cryoelectron microscopy, transmission electron microscope (TEM), manufacturing equipment, 3D printer, UV-Vis spectroscopy.
Brazil	Universidade Estadual de Campinas	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, mass spectroscopy (MS), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), gas chromatography (GC), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), 3D manufacturing, reactors.
Brazil	Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), Electron and optical microprobe, Universal electromechanical testing machine, X-ray diffraction (XRD), potentiostat/galvanostat, mass spectroscopy (MS), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Infrared spectroscopy (IR), gas chromatography (GC), Raman spectroscopy, Elemental analyzer, Mössbauer spectroscopy, Specific area analyzer, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Ion chromatography, photoreactors, bioreactors.
Brazil	Universidade Federal de São Carlos	X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Metal Additive Manufacturing Equipment, Multi-user Platform for obtaining powders through Ultrasonic Atomization and 3D Printing of Titanium, Multi-principal and Refractory Alloys.
Brazil	Universidade Federal do Parana	Gas chromatography (GC), N ₂ physisorption (BET and BJH), CO ₂ adsorption micropore analyzer, nanoparticle analyzer, low pressure bench reactor, hydrothermal reactors for catalyst synthesis, bench reactor and pilot scale prototype for hydrogen production by dry methane reforming, high pressure reactor, prototype for gas adsorption on porous solids at moderate pressures.
Brazil	Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), electron, ion and probe microscopy, Raman spectroscopy, materials synthesis equipment.
Brazil	Universidade de São Paulo	Gas chromatography (GC), elemental analyzer, X-ray diffraction (XRD), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), confocal microscopy, scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Brazil	Universidade Estadual Paulista "Júlio de Mesquita Filho"	X-ray diffraction (XRD), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), gas chromatography (GC), reactors, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.
Brazil	Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro	Gamma and X-ray radiation equipment, magnetometer, quantum optics equipment, crystallography equipment, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), mass spectroscopy (MS), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), potentiostat/galvanostat, scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Brazil	Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina	Organic molecule and material synthesis equipment, UV-Vis spectroscopy with multi-cell platforms, ultrasonic probe reactor, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), melting point determination equipment, laser pulse photolysis equipment, surface/pore analyzer, chemisorption analyzer.
Brazil	Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul	X-ray fluorescence (XRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, scanning electron microscope (SEM), Rutherford and Channeling Backscattering Spectrometry, Nuclear Reaction Analyzer, Particle-Induced X-Ray Emission, Optical Emission Spectrometers.
Brazil	Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte	Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), mass spectroscopy (MS), ultrasound equipment, conventional hydrothermal reactor, microwave-heated hydrothermal reactor, power grid analysis system, high-current and high-voltage test leads, prototyping system.
Brazil	Universidade de Brasília	Plasma reactor, plasma machine with magnetic mirrors and low-energy argon ion source, electron and liquid-phase ion spectroscopy, electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Mossbauer spectrometer, Raman spectroscopy, photoacoustic spectrometer and Superconducting Quantum Interference Device, 3D manufacturing, gas chromatography (GC)-MS.
Brazil	Universidade Federal de Itajubá	Heat treatment furnaces, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), UV-visible spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Karl Fischer coulometry, Calorimetric analysis, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, gas adsorption analyzer (BET), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, Ultraviolet spectroscopy, Electrolyzer.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Brazil	Universidade Federal Fluminense	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Hydrogen Gas Pressure Regulator, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Calorimetric Titrator, Dynamic Light Scattering and Zeta Potential, Surface Area Analyzer, Magnetic Chemisorption Inductor, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), UV-Vis spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy.
Chile	Universidad de Chile	Gas chromatography (GC), mass spectroscopy (MS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) with reaction cells, UV-Vis spectroscopy, reactors, characterization equipment for H ₂ , O ₂ , CO chemisorption, N ₂ O decomposition, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, membrane distiller.
Chile	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	Gas adsorption analyzer, gas chromatography (GC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), systems for determining metal dispersion and surface acidity, as well as equipment for cyclic voltammetry.
Chile	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso	Glove box with inert atmosphere, multi-parameter cell analyzer, high-precision electrometer.
Chile	Universidad de Santiago de Chile	Potentiostats, glove compartments with inert atmosphere, volumetric equipment with tube furnace and automated data acquisition system, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), confocal microscope, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, microwave-assisted sample digester.
Chile	Universidad de Antofagasta	Electrolizers, hydrogen processing equipment, fuel cells, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Atomic absorption spectroscopy.
Chile	Universidad Católica del Norte	Battery assembly presses, material coating machine, bipotentiostat and battery cycler, spectral confocal microscope, Atomic absorption spectroscopy.
Chile	Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María	Electrolyzers, H ₂ storage and supply units, reactors, lithium cells, scanning electron microscope (SEM), scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), fuel cells of various power, test benches for electric and hybrid motors, hydrogen charging stations.
Chile	Universidad de Talca	Hydrogen storage battery, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)-MS, gas chromatography (GC), reactors.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Chile	Universidad de Atacama	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), X-ray diffraction (XRD), magnesium extraction equipment in salt flats.
Chile	Universidad Autónoma de Chile	Electrochemical cells, 3D manufacturing.
Colombia	Universidad Nacional de Colombia	CHN/CHNS elemental analyzers, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), gas adsorption analyzer (BET), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), pyrolysis equipment, regulated power supplies, potentiostats, polarograph, fuel cell test station, gasification equipment.
Colombia	Universidad de Antioquia	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), transmission electron microscope (TEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), solar simulator, UV-Vis spectroscopy, micro Raman spectroscopy, potentiostat, tube furnace, semiconductor properties meter, Li-ion battery prototype, electrolysis equipment, fuel cells, hydride storage.
Colombia	Universidad de Los Andes	Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), fuel cells, gas chromatography (GC), UV-Vis spectroscopy, mass spectroscopy (MS), Vacuum Furnace, 3D Printer, Power Supply, Sonicator, Hydrogen Bus, Fuel Cells, Electrolyzers.
Colombia	Universidad EAFIT	Bio-inspired electrolyzer (own creation), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Colombia	Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana	Ultrasonic equipment, gas chromatography (GC), gas scrubber, CHONS Elemental Analyzer, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Colombia	Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Extractive Gas Analyzer, Particle Size and Zeta Potential Analyzer, Energy Audit Instruments, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Potentiostat.
Colombia	Universidad Industrial de Santander	X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, UV-Vis Spectroscopy, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Colombia	Universidad de Santander	Electrolizers, hydrogen equipment (home-made), gas chromatography (GC)-MS.
Colombia	Universidad de Córdoba	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Atomic Fluorescence Spectroscopy, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Microwave Digestion System, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry.
Colombia	Universidad del Atlántico	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, Microwave Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometer, Microwave Digester, UV-Vis Spectroscopy, Electrochemical Synthesis Equipment, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Electrocatalysis Equipment.
Costa Rica	Universidad de Costa Rica	X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), mass spectroscopy (MS), UV-Vis spectroscopy, solar panels, adsorption equipment, fuels analyzer, energy analyzer, gas analyzer, calorimeter, gas chromatography (GC), melting furnace, reactors, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy.
Costa Rica	Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), Optical Microscope, Stereoscope, Tomography equipment, Gas extraction chambers.
Costa Rica	National Laboratory of Nanotechnology LANOTEC	Chromatography systems, spectroscopy instruments, transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), thermal analysis equipment, mechanical testing instruments, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), 3D printers.
Ecuador	Eseuela Superior Politecnica del Litoral Ecuador	Fuel cell, hydrogen generator, synthesis furnaces, 3D manufacturing, three-phase power quality analyzer, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC).
Ecuador	Universidad de Cuenca	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, Lithium-ion Battery, Electrolyzer and Hydrogen Cells, Supercapacitors.
Ecuador	Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja	Gas analyzer, X-ray diffraction (XRD), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, gas chromatography (GC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).
Ecuador	Universidad de las Fuerzas Armadas ESPE	Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Electrochemical Study Station, UV-Vis spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), gas chromatography (GC), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Ecuador	Universidad Técnica de Ambato	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), Atomic Absorption spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).
Mexico	Instituto Politécnico Nacional	Hydrogen gas analyzer, gas chromatography (GC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Mexico	Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México	X-ray diffraction (XRD), Thermochemical properties analyzer, Microscope, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Electrochemistry, Energy storage, Atomic absorption spectroscopy, inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, Thin-film technology, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), solar cells, photovoltaic energy, energy conversion, 3D manufacturing, Raman spectroscopy, batteries.
Mexico	Tecnológico Nacional de México	Lithium cells, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC).
Mexico	Tecnológico de Monterrey	Gas chromatography (GC), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, Raman spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Chemisorption and physisorption Equipment, Z potential and particle size, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), Isotopic analysis.
Mexico	Centro de Investigación Científica de Yucatán	Atomic force microscopy (AFM), gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), UV-vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy. Elemental analyzer, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fixed bed reactor, Calcination kilns, potentiostats/galvanostats, Rotating ring and disk electrode system, Fuel cell evaluation stations, Texture analysis equipment.
Mexico	Instituto Nacional de Electricidad y Energías Limpias	Scanning electron microscope (SEM), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), gas chromatography (GC), Fuel cells, 3D manufacturing.
Mexico	Instituto Potosino de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica, A.C.	Transmission electron microscope (TEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), mass spectroscopy (MS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Raman spectroscopy, gas chromatography (GC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), microwave synthesis reactor, rotary tube furnace.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Mexico	Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla	Micro Raman spectroscopy, Profilometry, UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy, Time-Resolved Photoluminescence, Spectroscopic Ellipsometry, Semiconductor Characterization, Impedance Spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Quantum Efficiency analyzer, High Frequency Impedance Analyzer, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), mass spectroscopy (MS), X-ray diffraction (XRD), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.
Mexico	Centro de Investigación Científica y de Educación Superior de Ensenada	Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry-MS, High-precision water isotope analyzer, Determination of thermal properties of solid materials, Elemental analysis, scanning electron microscope (SEM).
Mexico	Centro de Investigación en Materiales Avanzados	Thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Thermomechanical analysis, scanning electron microscope (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), 3D manufacturing, Energy efficiency analysis, UV-Vis spectroscopy, gas chromatography (GC), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).
Mexico	Centro de Innovación Aplicada en Tecnologías Competitivas	Calorimetry, rheology, dynamic mechanical analysis, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), reverse osmosis and conventional and bipolar membrane electro dialysis.
Mexico	Centro de Investigaciones en Óptica, A.C.	Ultrasonic equipment, gas adsorption analyzer, UV-vis spectroscopy, TOC analyzer, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Potentiostat/Galvanostat, gas chromatography (GC), mass spectroscopy (MS).
Mexico	Universidad Autónoma del Estado de Morelos	Photoluminescence Spectroscopy, UV-Vis-NIR Spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Metal Evaporator, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Field Emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM), scanning electron microscope (SEM), manufacturing equipment.
Mexico	Instituto Mexicano del Petroleo	Manufacturing equipment, calcination equipment, gas separation equipment, textural properties analyzer, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), gas chromatography (GC), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry.
Mexico	Universidad Autónoma de Baja California	Isolated Photovoltaic System, Grid-connected Photovoltaic System, Concentrating Power Collector, Grid-connected Wind Power System, Hydrogen Power Generation System.

Country	Facility/Institute	Equipment
Mexico	Universidad Autónoma de Campeche	Ion chromatography, flue gas analyzer.
Mexico	Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, scanning electron microscope (SEM), optical and confocal microscope, high temperature heating furnaces, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), elemental chemical microanalysis, thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), gas adsorption analyzer (BET).
Mexico	Universidad Autónoma de Guadalajara	UV-Vis spectroscopy, gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), mass spectroscopy (MS), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR).
Mexico	Universidad Autónoma de Nayarit	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), vacuum melting furnace.
Mexico	Universidad de Guanajuato	Raman spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF).
Mexico	Universidad de Guadalajara	Energy logger, Energy analyzer, Power electronics simulator, 3D manufacturing.
Perú	Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú	Gas Analyzer, Distributed Generation System – Photovoltaic, Thermal Operating Parameter Logging, Power Grid Analyzer, Spark Optical Emission Spectrometer, Inverted Metallographic Microscope, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Potentiostat/Galvanostat.
Perú	Universidad de Ingeniería y Tecnología - UTEC	Atomic absorption spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-Vis spectroscopy, 3D Manufacturing, Energy and Power Meter, Flue Gas Analyzer.
Perú	Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería	Gas chromatography (GC)-MS, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Atomic absorption spectroscopy, UV-Vis Spectroscopy, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Equipment for assembling lithium batteries, equipment for the synthesis of battery electrode materials.
Perú	Universidad Nacional de San Agustín de Arequipa	Physisorption and micropore equipment, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)-thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), inductively coupled plasma (ICP) spectrometry -MS, Microwave digester.

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